

The Effects of Acetaminophen on *C. elegans* Longevity and Egg Count

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to understand the effects of acetaminophen on *Caenorhabditis elegans* lifespan and fertility. The experiment was based off the study [1] which assessed the effect of aspirin on the lifespan of *C. elegans*. The original study showed that aspirin causes stress in *C. elegans* similar to caloric restriction, resulting in increased stress resilience and prolonged longevity. Assuming that acetaminophen treatment invokes similar mechanism, the expectation was to observe prolonged lifespan and decreased egg production, one of the known stress outcomes in *C. elegans* [2]. Wildtype and *daf-9* mutant *C. elegans* were provided with OP50 *Escherichia coli* seeded plates containing a diluted concentration of acetaminophen and water at 50, 100, and 200 millimolars, each plate hosting 4 worms of the same type. The plates were assigned to 5 study groups: 3 treatment groups corresponding to each treatment concentration had 3 wildtype *C. elegans* plates each, 2 plates with untreated wildtype *C. elegans* were assigned as a control group, and 2 plates with *Daf-9* treatment group with 100mm acetaminophen concentration. The observed increased movement speed suggested that acetaminophen solution causes stress in *C. elegans* worms, however the increased egg production in the wildtype *C. elegans* treatment groups was also observed when compared to the control groups. The highest average egg production per worm was observed in the lowest concentration of acetaminophen treatment group subsequently declining as the concentration of acetaminophen increased, suggesting that either mild stress could be beneficial for *C. elegans* fertility or that acetaminophen also enhances *C. elegans* reproductive function. The results of this study showed that treating *C. elegans* with acetaminophen increased both, their egg production and lifespan, peaking at 50 and 200 millimolars concentration respectively, similar to the findings of the original study. Conducting the experiment only once and therefore not checking for the reproducibility and statistical significance of the results is the main limitation of the study.

Introduction

This experiment is built off a study published in Cell Reports earlier this year titled "Aspirin Recapitulates Features of Caloric Restriction in *C. elegans*". *C. elegans* are simple transparent nematode with a short two-week lifespan whose genes and molecular processes have similarities to more complex organisms like humans [3], making them a great model organism for toxicity studies. The original study concluded that adding aspirin to *C. elegans*' diet at the concentrations of 50, 100, and 200 μM increased their longevity, with the addition of aspirin at the concentration of 100 μM resulting in the longest lifespan. The objective of this experiment was to replicate the methodology of the original study with the addition of various concentrations of acetaminophen, commonly known as Tylenol, as an additional exposure.

Acetaminophen was chosen because unlike many other painkillers, which we know work by stopping the brain from receiving pain signals derived from the nerves, it is unknown how acetaminophen is processed. The results of this experiment could help us learn whether feeding *C. elegans* acetaminophen recapitulates features of caloric restriction in the same way that aspirin does, allowing the *C. elegans* to live for a longer period of time. The original hypothesis for my study was that the *C. elegans* consuming acetaminophen would exhibit a higher average lifespan, but the worms' fertility would be adversely affected and the number of eggs being laid would decrease. This experiment used both wildtype and *Daf-9* mutation worms. The *daf-9* mutation means that the worms are more stress resistant and have a longer lifespan [4] than the wildtype.

Methods

Four adult wild type worms were placed onto each of the eleven OP50 *E. coli* seeded plates and four adult *Daf-9* were placed onto each of the two OP50 *E. coli* seeded plates using a transferring pick. Once all of the worms were distributed among the plates, they were counted and observed. The plates with wild type *C. Elegans* were divided among three treatment groups and a control group: each treatment group was assigned three individual plates and two remaining plates were assigned to a control group. Each treatment group corresponded to a specific acetaminophen solution concentration: 50, 100 and 200 millimolars. The two plates with *Daf-9* were treated with the 100 μM concentration. There was no untreated control group for *Daf-9* type, and therefore the comparison group for the *Daf-9* worm was a wild type treatment group with the same concentration.

After the original setup of the experiment, each group was observed every twenty-four hours using a microscope, the survival rate, egg count and movement speed were recorded. The worms were transferred to the new plates every other day to separate the original worms from the newly hatched progeny. Ideally, the observational period should have lasted until all of the worms in all groups were dead.

Results

The results of this experiment are shown in the figures below. Figure #1 shows large variation in the average number of eggs laid per worm per day among wildtype *C. elegans* plates, with acetaminophen concentrations 50mm and 200mm. The highest egg count was observed at 50mm acetaminophen concentration: relative to the two controls, wildtype *C. elegans* 50mm plate 2 exhibited a 6-fold increase in average eggs laid per worm. The lowest egg count was observed at 200mm acetaminophen concentration, plate 3. However, as depicted in Figure 2, when the egg count per worm is averaged over all plates with the same type of *C. elegans* and acetaminophen concentration, the highest number of eggs was laid by wildtype *C. elegans* with the lowest acetaminophen concentration, declining as the acetaminophen concentration is increasing. Nevertheless, the average number of eggs laid by *C. elegans* exposed to the treatment with the highest concentration was still higher than the number of eggs laid by the control group. *Daf-9* group treated with a 100mm acetaminophen solution had the lowest egg count.

Figure #1, Average Number of Eggs Laid per Worm per Day in Each OP50 *E. coli* seeded plate.

Figure #2, Average Number of Eggs Laid per Worm per Day per Acetaminophen Concentration Group.

The individual plates' survival rates are shown in Figure #3. Although the days are not evenly spaced apart due to the time and day at which the amount alive were checked, the graph still shows results as all the worms from the control groups did not survive for the time equivalent to

the groups given acetaminophen. 200mm wildtype *C. elegans* plate #1 had the highest survival rate for most of the observation points.

Averaging survival rate over all plates with the same *C. elegans* type and treatment concentration, as shown in Figure 4 makes the interpretation of the results easier. 100mm *Daf-9* and wildtype control group have the lowest survival rates.

Figure #3, Percentage of worms alive in each OP50 *E. coli* seeded plate.

Figure #4, Percentage of worms alive averaged over all groups with the same acetaminophen concentration.

Discussion

Based on the results, we can conclude that providing *C. elegans* acetaminophen increases both, the lifespan and egg production. This conclusion could be potentially strengthened by performing the statistical tests to test for a statistically significant difference between survival rates and the number of eggs laid of the acetaminophen treated groups.

The longevity results are similar to the results of the original study using aspirin: both substances result in the increased worms' longevity, with 100 mm aspirin concentration and 200 mm acetaminophen concentration producing the longest lifespan. However, the original study did not examine the effect of aspirin on worms' fertility, which was one of measured outcomes of this study. Based on the results of this experiment, the concentration of 50 mm is optimal for the maximum egg production with the number of eggs decreasing as the concentration is increased which may imply that mild stress is beneficial for the wildtype *C. elegans* fertility. Alternatively, acetaminophen might have fertility enhancing qualities.

Observed movements that quickly go from a rapid to slow pace could be an indication that acetaminophen causes stress on the worms. This would also explain why the Daf-9 worms at a concentration of 100 mm produce fewer offspring than the wildtype worms at the same acetaminophen concentration.

It is possible that the primary source of high outcome variation is human error. The greatest opportunity for error that could impact results was transferring the *C. elegans* from one plate to another. In case the wrong worms are transferred, it would later appear as if the worms survived longer than the original worms in the treatment group that were given acetaminophen. Along with damaging the integrity of the results, it could also potentially change the egg count and possibly change the movement patterns. In addition to potential error due to transferring the worm subject from the wrong group, pressing or scraping too hard while transferring the worms could result in damage and premature death of the worm. Other sources of potential error would be miscounting the number of eggs or worms as well as worms dying from other causes.

If this experiment were to be replicated, multiple steps in the experiment setup could be revised and improved to strengthen the results. Firstly, the experiment should have a longer follow-up period until all of the worms die. Secondly, a greater number of concentration groups and number of worm subjects in each plate would improve the generalizability of the results. And finally, having a control group for Daf-9 type, not available in this iteration of the experiment, would make for a one-to-one comparison between the two types of worms. However, most importantly, to test for the reproducibility of the results and whether detected

differences in longevity and egg count are not due to chance, the experiment would have to be repeated multiple times.

Conclusions

Adding acetaminophen to the *C. elegans* diet results in increased average lifespan and greater fertility, as more eggs are being laid peaking at 200 and 50 mm concentration respectively. The experimental data confirms the original hypothesis that the lifespan would increase, however these findings do not support the original assumption that acetaminophen results in fewer eggs laid.

References

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